

Modeling of aqueous phase adsorption: Is it time to bid adieu to the Harkins–Jura isotherm?

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Abstract

The Harkins–Jura isotherm equation was originally developed to interpret sigmoid or type II isotherms exhibited by gas-solid adsorption systems. Surprisingly, in the field of water contaminant adsorption, it has been exclusively used to describe hyperbolic or type I isotherms since the mid-2000s. Given the availability of several isotherm models capable of handling type I data, we must ask ourselves: Is there a need for the Harkins–Jura isotherm? To gain acceptance into the pool of curve-fitting models for type I data, the Harkins–Jura isotherm must demonstrate superiority over existing, well-established models. When pitted against the grand masters of such models, i.e., the Langmuir and Freundlich equations, the Harkins–Jura isotherm was found to be distinctly inferior in the modeling of type I adsorption data with and without an apparent plateau. Worse still, the Harkins–Jura isotherm was also found to perform poorly in the correlation of sigmoid or type II data, which was its original intended purpose. Given its very limited modeling power, we argue that it is time to bid adieu to the mediocre Harkins–Jura isotherm.

Keywords: Hyperbolic isotherm; Sigmoid isotherm; Type I isotherm; Type II isotherm; Aranovich–Donohue isotherm

1. Introduction

The Harkins–Jura (HJ) isotherm was developed in the mid-1940s for multilayer adsorption of gases, and extensive use has been made of this isotherm to calculate the surface area of a solid [1,2]. Since the mid-2000s, it has been applied to the interpretation of an increasing number of experimental isotherms for water contaminant adsorption on solid media. A 2004 paper was among the first to apply the HJ isotherm to aqueous phase adsorption data [3]. Since then, many such studies have been published across a broad spectrum of scholarly journals (e.g., *Chemical Engineering Journal* [4–7], *Journal of Hazardous Materials* [8–10], *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* [11–16], and *Journal of Molecular Liquids* [17–27]).

Although the two-parameter HJ isotherm is normally used to describe sigmoid or type II isotherm data in gas phase adsorption research, it has been exclusively used to interpret hyperbolic or type I data in aqueous phase adsorption studies. A linear version of the HJ isotherm is popularly used to fit experimental data by means of linear regression. Its two adjustable parameters can be estimated from the slope and intercept of a linear plot.

There are several two-parameter isotherm models that give good agreement with type I data. Prominent examples include the Langmuir, Freundlich, and Dubinin–Radushkevich equations. How competitive is the HJ isotherm against these proven isotherm models in the modeling of type I data? The HJ isotherm will be a valuable modeling tool if it can outperform the widely used Langmuir and Freundlich equations.

Although many studies have compared the HJ, Langmuir, and Freundlich isotherms in the fitting of type I data, the reported results are not meaningful. This is due to the fact that

linear forms of these models were fitted to different sets of transformed data. In most cases, the experimental data were expressed as c/q versus c for the Langmuir isotherm fit, $\ln(q)$ versus $\ln(c)$ for the Freundlich isotherm fit, and $1/q^2$ versus $\ln(c)$ for the HJ isotherm fit (q is the adsorbed phase concentration and c is the aqueous phase concentration). To obtain an unbiased comparison, the three models should be judged on their ability to describe the same form of data.

It is the purpose of this paper to evaluate the ability of the HJ isotherm to interpret type I data in an unbiased manner. To this end, the HJ, Langmuir, and Freundlich isotherms are compared using experimental data expressed in the form of q versus c . Furthermore, this work reports on the modeling of type II data using the HJ isotherm. Its performance is compared to that of the Aranovich–Donohue isotherm, which is known for its ability to describe such curves. In the literature of water contaminant adsorption, the HJ isotherm does not seem to have been applied to type II data.

2. Isotherm models and data fitting

2.1. The Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms

The Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms and their commonly used linear forms are given by Eqs. (1)–(4), where q is the adsorbed phase concentration, c is the aqueous phase concentration at equilibrium, b and q_m are Langmuir fitting constants, and k and n are Freundlich fitting constants.

$$q = \frac{q_m bc}{1 + bc} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{c}{q} = \frac{1}{q_m b} + \frac{1}{q_m} c \quad (2)$$

$$q = kc^n \quad (3)$$

$$\ln(q) = \ln(k) + n \ln(c) \quad (4)$$

2.2. The Harkins–Jura (HJ) isotherm

This isotherm equation [1,2,28], devised for multilayer adsorption of gases, is given by Eq. (5), where p is the gas pressure, p_0 is the saturation pressure of the gas, v is the volume of gas adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent at pressure p , v_0 is the volume of gas adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent at pressure p_0 , and A is a constant. Eq. (5) may be rewritten as Eq. (6), where $B = \ln(p_0) + A/v_0^2$.

$$\ln\left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right) = A\left(\frac{1}{v_0^2} - \frac{1}{v^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\ln(p) = B - \frac{A}{v^2} \quad (6)$$

For aqueous phase adsorption, Eq. (6) is rewritten as Eq. (7). A commonly used linear form of the HJ isotherm is given by Eq. (8), which suggests that a plot of $1/q^2$ against $\ln(c)$ should yield a straight line if the data follow the HJ isotherm. Rearranging Eq. (7) leads to Eq. (9), which is nonlinear in the two fitting parameters A and B .

$$\ln(c) = B - \frac{A}{q^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{q^2} = \frac{B}{A} - \frac{1}{A} \ln(c) \quad (8)$$

$$q = \sqrt{\frac{A}{B - \ln(c)}} \quad (9)$$

2.3. The Aranovich–Donohue (AD) isotherm

Like the HJ isotherm, the AD isotherm [29] was also developed for multilayer adsorption of gases. One version of the AD isotherm, adapted for aqueous phase adsorption, is written as Eq. (10), where q_m and b are the Langmuir constants and k_A and n_A are fitting parameters. The AD isotherm has recently been shown to fit several aqueous phase adsorption isotherms with high accuracy [30,31].

$$q = \frac{q_m bc}{(1 + bc)(1 - k_A c)^{n_A}} \quad (10)$$

2.4. Data fitting

Several sets of experimental data, taken from the literature of water contaminant adsorption, were fitted to the isotherm models investigated in this work using a linear or nonlinear regression method. The software GraphPad Prism version 9 for Windows was used for all data fitting.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Linear fits of type I data

Fig. 1. Isotherm fits of reactive red 195 adsorption data [32] by linear regression. (A) Langmuir [Eq. (2)]. (B) Freundlich [Eq. (4)]. (C) HJ [Eq. (8)].

To compare the data fitting attributes of the Freundlich, Langmuir, and HJ isotherms, a type I experimental isotherm was selected from the recent work of Munagapati et al. [32]. The experimental isotherm depicts the adsorption of reactive red 195 by a chemically modified lychee peel adsorbent, measured at 298 K. Following the conventional modeling approach, the linear forms of the Langmuir [Eq. (2)], Freundlich [Eq. (4)], and HJ [Eq. (8)] were fitted to the dye adsorption data, as shown in Fig. 1. The resulting parameter estimates are presented in

Table 1. According to the R^2 scores given in Fig. 1, the Langmuir isotherm fit is near-perfect, returning an R^2 of 0.999. With an R^2 value of 0.942, the Freundlich isotherm fit is inferior to the Langmuir fit. The worst performer is the HJ isotherm fit, returning an R^2 value of 0.701. The experimental data plotted according to the linearized HJ isotherm, Eq. (8), is markedly nonlinear in shape.

Table 1. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the linearized Langmuir, Freundlich, and HJ isotherms to reactive red 195 adsorption data [32].

Isotherm	Equation	Parameter	Value
Langmuir	(2)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	0.115
		q_m (mg g ⁻¹)	146.2
Freundlich	(4)	k (mg g ⁻¹)(L mg ⁻¹) ^{n}	30.01
		n	0.351
HJ	(8)	A (mg g ⁻¹) ²	4347.83
		B	4.13

Fig. 2. Isotherm curves calculated using linear regression-generated parameter estimates. (A) Langmuir [Eq. (1)]. (B) Freundlich [Eq. (3)]. (C) HJ [Eq. (9)].

However, the R^2 values obtained by the linear regression method should not be used to compare the three isotherms because they indicate how well the three isotherms fitted different sets of transformed data. Unbiased results can be obtained if the three isotherms are compared

using a common form of the experimental data. An obvious way to do that is to assess how well the three isotherms track the untransformed data plotted in the form of q versus c . Fig. 2 displays the q versus c curves calculated from the nonlinear forms of the three isotherms using the linear regression-generated parameter estimates listed in Table 1.

Fig. 2 suggests that the Langmuir isotherm is the best-performing model, but the R^2 value of 0.987 (Fig. 2A) is smaller than the near-perfect R^2 score seen in Fig. 1A. Furthermore, Fig. 2B confirms that the Freundlich isotherm is inferior to the Langmuir isotherm, and the R^2 value of 0.863 is noticeably smaller than the R^2 score given in Fig. 1B. The superiority of the Langmuir isotherm over the Freundlich isotherm in this case is due to the fact that the experimental isotherm exhibits an apparent plateau at large values of c . While the Langmuir isotherm is designed to predict a plateau at large values of c , this is not the case for the Freundlich isotherm, for which $q \rightarrow \infty$ when $c \rightarrow \infty$.

In the case of the HJ isotherm, Fig. 2C shows that the calculated curve is definitely not of hyperbolic shape. Because of the very poor linear fit, as seen in Fig. 1C, the linear regression-generated parameter estimates are nonsensical. Note that it is not possible to calculate an R^2 value for the HJ isotherm because the last two data points could not be accounted for. The values of the term “ $\ln(c)$ ” in Eq. (9), for the last two data points, are greater than the fitted value of B , resulting in negative numbers. Eq. (9) breaks down since the square roots of negative real numbers do not exist in the real numbers. Visually, one can see in Fig. 2 that the HJ isotherm is the worst performer among the three isotherms, but a quantitative comparison based on the R^2 metric is not possible. Without plotting the q versus c curve, the nonsensical value of B would have gone unnoticed. It is therefore not advisable to compare the three isotherms based on their linear fits alone. However, the practice of comparing the goodness of linear fits is widespread in this field of research.

3.2. Nonlinear fits of type I data

As previously stated, fitting different linearized isotherm models to experimental data using linear regression is insufficient. The job is only half done. To compare the linearized isotherm models objectively, the linear regression step should be followed by plotting q versus c curves using the linear regression-generated parameter estimates. However, we have seen from the previous analysis in Section 3.1 that other problems could still crop up using this model comparison approach. A quantitative assessment of the q versus c curves plotted in Fig. 2 according to the R^2 metric is not possible due to the breakdown of the HJ isotherm defined by Eq. (9).

All the hassles noted above will disappear if we abandon the use of linearized isotherm equations in model comparison. It is straightforward to fit the nonlinear forms of the three isotherms to the reactive red 195 adsorption data by means of nonlinear regression. Fig. 3 shows such a data fitting approach, and the resulting parameter estimates are presented in Table 2. It is evident that the Langmuir isotherm is the best-performing one among the three isotherm models. The Freundlich nonlinear fit is inferior to the Langmuir nonlinear fit, reflecting the former's inability to track the apparent plateau at large values of c . The HJ isotherm is clearly the worst performer, revealing its limitations as a model for type I adsorption data.

Comparing the R^2 values in Figs. 2A and 3A reveals that there is little difference between the results obtained by the linearized Langmuir isotherm [Eq. (2)] and the nonlinear Langmuir isotherm [Eq. (1)]. However, the nonlinear Freundlich isotherm [Eq. (3)] is clearly superior to the linearized Freundlich isotherm [Eq. (4)], as revealed by the R^2 scores given in Figs. 2B and 3B. Needless to say, the nonlinear HJ isotherm is much superior to the linearized HJ isotherm. As previously mentioned, it is not possible to construct a complete q versus c curve in Fig. 2C.

Fig. 3. Isotherm fits of reactive red 195 adsorption data [32] by nonlinear regression. (A) Langmuir [Eq. (1)]. (B) Freundlich [Eq. (3)]. (C) HJ [Eq. (9)].

Table 2. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the nonlinear forms of the Langmuir, Freundlich, and HJ isotherms to reactive red 195 adsorption data [32].

Isotherm	Equation	Parameter	Value
Langmuir	(1)	b (L mg^{-1})	0.111
		q_m (mg g^{-1})	145.4
Freundlich	(3)	k ($\text{mg g}^{-1}(\text{L mg}^{-1})^n$)	39.32
		n	0.273
HJ	(9)	A ($\text{mg g}^{-1})^2$	21279
		B	5.88

Another set of type I data analyzed here, taken from the work of Ma et al. [33], describes the adsorption of the antibiotic tetracycline on a biochar adsorbent. Unlike the reactive red 195 isotherm depicted in Fig. 3, the tetracycline isotherm does not exhibit an apparent plateau at large values of c , as can be seen in Fig. 4. The Freundlich isotherm, which predicts that q increases indefinitely with c , excels at fitting isotherm shapes of this type. Therefore, it is not surprising to see that the Freundlich isotherm fit (Fig. 4B, $R^2 = 0.992$) is much superior to the Langmuir isotherm fit (Fig. 4B, $R^2 = 0.933$) in correlating the tetracycline adsorption data. Fig. 4C shows that the HJ isotherm fit can follow the data trend fairly well, but the R^2 value of 0.919 is the worst one among the three R^2 scores. The resulting parameter estimates are presented in

Table 3. Figs. 3 and 4 confirm that the HJ isotherm is vastly inferior to the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms in correlating the adsorption data with and without an apparent plateau.

Fig. 4. Isotherm fits of tetracycline adsorption data [33] by nonlinear regression. (A) Langmuir [Eq. (1)]. (B) Freundlich [Eq. (3)]. (C) HJ [Eq. (9)].

Table 3. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the nonlinear forms of the Langmuir, Freundlich, and HJ isotherms to tetracycline adsorption data [33].

Isotherm	Equation	Parameter	Value
Langmuir	(1)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	0.076
		q_m (mg g ⁻¹)	190.7
Freundlich	(3)	k (mg g ⁻¹)(L mg ⁻¹) ^{n}	42.89
		n	0.298
HJ	(9)	A (mg g ⁻¹) ²	33246
		B	5.86

3.3. Nonlinear fits of type II data

As previously mentioned, the HJ isotherm was originally devised to describe type II isotherms. In the field of water contaminant adsorption, practically all applications of the HJ isotherm have focused on type I isotherms. The HJ isotherm's ability to fit aqueous phase type II isotherms has not been reported. Here, the HJ isotherm is used to interpret previously published type II data. Its performance is compared to that of the Aranovich–Donohue (AD) isotherm, which has been shown to excel at fitting isotherm curves of this type [30,31].

Fig. 5A shows the fit of the HJ isotherm to the isotherm data obtained for the adsorption of reactive blue 5G on an orange bagasse biosorbent at 40 °C, as reported by Fiorentin et al. [34]. The resulting parameter estimates are presented in Table 4. As can be seen in Fig. 5A, with an R^2 value of 0.959, the HJ isotherm can track the overall sigmoid profile reasonably well. The AD isotherm fit, by comparison, is much more effective, returning an R^2 score of 0.989. Fig. 5B shows that the isotherm curve predicted by the AD isotherm, calculated using the parameter estimates given in Table 4, is in excellent agreement with the experimental data. The HJ isotherm fit is noticeably inferior to the AD isotherm fit.

The comparison based on the R^2 metric is somewhat biased because it does not account for the fact that the HJ and AD isotherms have different numbers of fitting parameters. The AD isotherm with four fitting parameters is expected to outperform the HJ isotherm with two fitting parameters. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) [35] provides a more objective way to compare isotherm models with different numbers of parameters. According to the AIC test, the model with the largest Akaike weight is the best-performing one in a group of competing models with different numbers of fitting parameters. The Akaike weights calculated for the HJ and AD isotherm fits are, respectively, 2.7% and 97.3%. The AIC test favors the AD isotherm over the HJ isotherm, justifying the use of four parameters to fit the dye isotherm data.

Fig. 5. Isotherm fits of reactive blue 5G adsorption data [34] by nonlinear regression. (A) HJ [Eq. (9)]. (B) AD [Eq. (10)].

Table 4. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the nonlinear forms of the HJ and AD isotherms to reactive blue 5G adsorption data [34].

Isotherm	Equation	Parameter	Value
HJ	(9)	A (mg g^{-1}) ²	1213
		B	4.936
AD	(10)	b (L mg^{-1})	0.154
		q_m (mg g^{-1})	35.0
		k_A (L mg^{-1})	0.008
		n_A	0.354

Another set of type II isotherm data, taken from the work of Manera et al. [36], is used to compare the HJ and AD isotherms. The selected data set depicts the adsorption of acid red 357 by an activated carbon adsorbent. Fig. 6 illustrates the fits of the two isotherms to the dye adsorption data. The resulting parameter estimates are given in Table 5. Fig. 6A shows that the HJ isotherm fit is somewhat poor; the R^2 score is less than 0.9. There are significant deviations between the predicted sigmoid curve and experimental data in the low concentration range ($c < 200 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$). By contrast, the performance of the AD isotherm is excellent ($R^2 = 0.995$), as can be seen in Fig. 6B. The Akaike weights for the HJ and AD isotherm fits are 0.1% and 99.9%, respectively. The two-parameter HJ isotherm is wholly inadequate for correlating this type II isotherm.

Fig. 6. Isotherm fits of acid red 357 adsorption data [36] by nonlinear regression. (A) HJ [Eq. (9)]. (B) AD [Eq. (10)].

Table 5. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the nonlinear forms of the HJ and AD isotherms to acid red 357 adsorption data [36].

Isotherm	Equation	Parameter	Value
HJ	(9)	A (mg g^{-1}) ²	29899
		B	6.726
AD	(10)	b (L mg^{-1})	0.626
		q_m (mg g^{-1})	189.3
		k_A (L mg^{-1})	0.0013
		n_A	0.278

In summary, given that the HJ isotherm was originally developed to interpret type II data, using it to describe type I data can be considered a case of misapplication. We mention in passing that several isotherm models (Dubinin–Radushkevich; Frumkin–Fowler–Guggenheim; Kiselev; Temkin; Elovich; Hill; Sips; Koble–Corrigan; Liu; Radke–Prausnitz) have also been misused in this field of research [37–43].

4. Conclusions

The domain of aqueous phase adsorption has “borrowed” several isotherm models from the field of gas phase adsorption. Unfortunately, some of these isotherm models have been misused. For instance, in gas adsorption research, the HJ isotherm was originally devised to interpret sigmoid or type II isotherm data. In water contaminant adsorption research, it has been exclusively used to fit hyperbolic or type I isotherm data. Consequently, it is not surprising to observe that the HJ isotherm was inferior to the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms in the modeling of type I adsorption data. The thing is, the performance of the HJ isotherm was also poor when applied to type II adsorption data. It was found to be markedly inferior to the Aranovich–Donohue isotherm. With far more effective alternatives available, justification for the use of the HJ isotherm in data correlation cannot be made. Accordingly, we call upon the environmental adsorption community to bid adieu to the mediocre HJ isotherm.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests.

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